

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF TRACTOR OPERATED SORGHUM HARVESTER

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Abstract:

Sorghum harvesting is a crucial operation that has a substantial impact on the crop's yield, quality, and financial return. Delays in harvesting may associate considerable or even severe losses due to over maturity or any unforeseen natural adversity. Early harvesting could open up opportunities for extra revenues through farming of short duration others crops in the gap between two major crops. This study evaluated the performance of a front-mounted tractor-operated sorghum harvester with the objective of reducing labor costs, time and losses in sorghum harvesting operations. The cutting efficiency was observed as decreased with increased forward speed and conveying efficiency observed was decreased with increased forward speed. The average effective field capacity and field efficiency of the sorghum harvester was found in the range of 0.342 ha/h and 79.72% respectively. The average cutting efficiency, average conveying efficiency and shattering losses of the sorghum harvester was found in the range of 97.34 to 99.36 %, 96.22 to 97.67 % and 0.39 to 0.43 % respectively. The average cost of operation of sorghum harvester was found Rs.750 per h and Rs.2200 per ha.

Keywords: Performance, Sorghum, Harvester, Field efficiency, Mechanization

Introduction

Sorghum, a versatile cereal crop with a rich history spanning thousands of years, has become an integral part of global agriculture due to its adaptability and diverse applications. Sorghum continues to gain prominence as a versatile crop used for food, animal feed and biofuel production. In India, sorghum's total area, production and productivity in 2023-2024 was 36.47 Lakh ha, 40.34 Lakh tones and 1106 kg/ha, respectively. In Maharashtra area, production and productivity of Sorghum was 16.00 lakh ha, 14.04 Lakh tones and 878 kg/ha, respectively. According to Table 1.1, Maharashtra accounts for 14.04 per cent of India's total production and 34.80 per cent of the country's sorghum (Department of Economics and Statistics, DA&FW, Gov., New Delhi.). Maharashtra leads in India in terms of sorghum crop area, production and productivity, followed by Karnataka, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu and so forth. In Vidharbha region of Maharashtra area, production and productivity of sorghum was 543 ha, 436.25 tones and 802.57 kg/ha, respectively during 2022-23 (DES, 2022-23).

Currently, land preparation, seeding and weeding are somewhat automated while harvesting is not since a suitable sorghum harvester is not readily available. Historically, sorghum was harvested using manual techniques that were labor-intensive and time-consuming. This process typically involved cutting the stalks with hand tools such as sickles or knives. While these traditional methods are still practiced in some regions, particularly in small-scale farming operations or areas with limited access to modern technology, they often result in considerable grain loss and inefficiency.

Heavy rainfall or storms during the harvest season can delay the process and reduce grain quality. Sorghum plants are often tall and prone to lodging (falling over), particularly after heavy rains or strong winds. Lodged crops are harder to harvest efficiently, leading to grain losses. The need for skilled labor to manage the harvest and use of mechanized equipment is a constraint in many regions, especially where the farm labor force is aging or migration trends reduce available workers. (Nikam *et al.*, 2017) and (Alizadeh *et al.*, 2007). Harvesting equipment that is self-propelled, powered by a tiller and mounted on a tractor has been designed for crops like paddy, wheat, soybeans, etc. however it cannot be utilized for sorghum because of the distinct crop structure. Harvesting restrictions of crops include high moisture content, severe lodging, stem diameter, uneven crop height, variety, a stalk's exposure to bending, crop conveyance, weight distribution and other which also limits the mechanization of sorghum harvesting. The current combine harvester is too costly, small and marginal farmers cannot afford it. Harvesting losses by combine harvesters are very high, resulting in a decline in yield. Furthermore, sorghum stalks get

damage and wastage that cannot be used as fodder for animals. The soil compaction issue is also associated with combine harvester fields. Indian farmers who practice dryland farming and have few resources for investment are unwilling to alter the way they currently harvest their sorghum. Small farmland holdings, an inadequate approach route to the field and harvesting mechanization limitations. The development of sorghum harvesters in India has significant potential due to the importance of sorghum (jowar) as a staple crop. Since there is not a successful machine in India so for harvesting sorghum plants and earheads, and hence developed inventions will address issues with current techniques. The evolution of sorghum harvesting techniques has played a pivotal role in maximizing yield, reducing post-harvest losses and enhancing overall production efficiency. This progression from traditional manual methods to advanced mechanized systems has significantly impacted the cultivation and utilization of this important crop.

By keeping all those facts, limitations in harvesting and today's need present investigations have been undertaken study performance evaluation of tractor operated sorghum harvester.

Review Of Literature

The harvester's performance has been greatly affected by the machine, the crop and the operational parameters. The findings of the performance evaluation of sorghum harvester harvesting machineries are reviewed below after a critical evaluation.

Butle (2011) evaluated the performance of tractor operated sorghum harvester and reported that the cutting efficiency and field efficiency was 76.92 per cent and 74.13 per cent with 2.5 km/h speed of operation respectively.

Nalawade *et al.*, (2009) conducted the functional trials of tractor operated reaper in mature jowar fields. The field trials were conducted as per the standard procedure laid down in RNAM test code. The average field capacity of the machine was found to be 0.4 ha/h, with a field efficiency of 73%. Fuel consumption was observed at 3.23 liters per hour.

Thakare and Saraf (2014) evaluated tractor operated sorghum harvester. They reported that, the total saving on labour and cost requirement in mechanical harvesting over traditional was 80 per cent and 82.66 per cent respectively.

Mareppa (2017) found that three ranges of moisture contents (9, 11, and 13%), forward speeds (2, 2.5 and 3 km/h) and header speeds (90, 120 and 140 cycles per min) were optimized based on minimized header loss, conveying loss, and windrowing loss in the study. For the crops bajra and sorghum, the optimum moisture content was 13%, with a forward speed of 2 km/h and a header speed of 90 cycles per minute.

Field efficiency and theoretical effective field capacity were found to be 88.24 & 85.26 % and 0.30 & 0.324 ha/h, respectively.

Jalu *et al.*, (2020) evaluated a manually drom engine powered fodder crop harvester. Three different forward speeds (0.3-0.6, 0.6-0.9 and 0.9-1.2 km/h) were used for the test performance. The maximum cutting efficiency (96.06%), field efficiency (81.47%) and minimum plant damage (7.08%) were found in the speed range of 0.6-0.9 km/h.

Material And Methods

The tractor operated sorghum harvester was developed at the Department of Farm Power and Machinery, Dr. PDKV, Akola. The developed sorghum harvester's major parts include the cutting unit, conveyor unit, power transmission system, supporting frame, crop row divider and star wheel. When the sorghum harvester moves through the sorghum field, crop row divider first penetrates in to standing sorghum crops and divides the crops. The star wheel through star wheel arms push sorghum stalks towards the cutter bar. The cutter bar cuts the sorghum stalks the few centimeter above the ground using a slider crank mechanism to reciprocate sets of knives moving between ledgers and the harvested sorghum stalks are conveyed through a canvas conveyor lugged belt at the desired speed. Finally, windrow harvested the sorghum crop at a right angle to the direction of operation.

The performance of the tractor operated sorghum harvester was evaluated in sorghum field. The testing and evaluation methodology outlined in IS: 11467(1985): test code for cereal harvesting machines was properly followed for evaluating the performance of the developed sorghum harvester.

Preliminary preparations

Prior to field testing, the sorghum harvester had been inspected for bearings, drives, and other moving parts, as well as various adjustments and bolt and nut tightness. The machine was run for 10 minutes at no load to allow for visual inspection and any adjustment if necessary.

Before harvesting of the sorghum crop in field by tractor operated harvester, the crop entire border of sorghum field was cut manually so as to facilitate the windrowing of first cut of sorghum stalks at right side on the ground. The working of developed tractor operated sorghum harvester shown in Pate 1.

Plate 1. Working front view tractor operated sorghum harvester in

During and after the harvesting operation, the following observations and data recorded. Following measurements of different parameters were taken during the evaluation.

Height of cut

The cutting height of the sorghum stalk was measured in the field after harvesting of the sorghum crop (Bawatharani *et al.*, 2016). The measurements were taken randomly at different places in the sorghum harvested field is shown in Plate 3.

Forward speed of operation

Two poles 20 meters apart were positioned approximately in the center of the test run to determine the forward speed of a tractor operated sorghum harvester. On the other side, two poles were set in a similar manner 20 m apart, forming four rectangular corners parallel to the

long side of the plot. The speed was estimated using the time it took for the driver to cross the distance (20 m) between two poles. The average of such readings was used to compute the forward speed of a tractor-operated sorghum harvester. The forward speed of operation was measured by observing the distance traveled and the time taken and computed using the following formula (Mehta *et al.*, 2005).

$$S = \frac{L}{T} \quad \dots(1)$$

Where,

S - forward speed, m/s

L - distance travelled, m

T - time taken to travel, sec

Width of cut

The width of the cut of the sorghum harvester was measured by measuring 5 m of steel tape. The operating width of the machine was measured at 5 randomly selected places in the field, and the average reading was recorded. Row-to-row spacing and the number of rows harvested are also considered for the actual working width of harvesting.

Turning time at headland

The turning time of the sorghum harvester was recorded by stopwatch at the headland of the sorghum field while turning. Time was recorded five times at both ends of the field.

Effective field capacity

Effective field capacity is the actual rate of performance of crop harvesting in a given time, based on total field time. To calculate effective field capacity, the time spent on actual work and the time lost on additional operations such as removing cutting crops and weeds when clogged. Actual field capacity was determined by dividing the actual average rate of field covering by the amount of time spent cutting (lost + productive). The effective field capacity was determined using the equation below (Debnath, *et al.*, 2020).

$$EFC = \frac{\text{Area covered, ha}}{\text{Time, h}} \quad \dots(2)$$

Where,

EFC - effective field capacity, ha/h

A - area covered, ha

T - time, h

Theoretical field capacity

The theoretical field capacity was determined by considering into account the working width and travel speed of the sorghum harvester. Theoretical field capacity was calculated by using following formula (Mehta *et al.*, 2005).

$$TFC = \frac{S \times W}{10} \quad \dots(3)$$

Where,

S - Speed of travel, km/h

W - Theoretical width, m

Field efficiency

Field efficiency was calculated by taking ratio of effective field capacity to theoretical field capacity. It is always expressed in percentage. This indicates lost time in the field and failure to utilize of the machine's working width (Singh *et al.*, 1988).

It was calculated by following formula (Mehta *et al.*, 2005).

$$FE = \frac{EFC}{TFC} \times 100 \quad \dots(4)$$

Where,

FE - field efficiency, %

EFC - effective field capacity, ha/ h

TFC - theoretical field capacity, ha/h

Cutting efficiency

The cutting efficiency of sorghum harvester is defined as the ratio of the total number of cut plants to the total number of plants present before the cutting operation in the field (Tanti *et al.*, 2019). In order to

determine the cutting efficiency of the sorghum harvester, the total number of sorghum plants was measured in 10 m row length before and after the sorghum harvesting operation in the sorghum field. It was determined by using following formula.

$$\text{Cutting efficiency (\%)} = \frac{N_1 - N_2}{N_1} \times 100 \quad \dots(5)$$

Where,

N_1 - number of plants in 10 m row length before sorghum harvesting
 N_2 - number of plants in 10 m row length after sorghum harvesting

Conveying efficiency

The conveying efficiency of the sorghum harvester is defined as the ratio of the total number of conveyed sorghum stalks to the total number of plants present before harvesting. To determine the conveying efficacy of the sorghum harvester, the total number of sorghum stalks in a 10-meter row length before harvesting and the total number of sorghum stalks in the same 10-meter row length that were not conveyed by the harvester's conveyor unit after harvesting were counted. The conveying efficiency of the sorghum harvester was calculated by the following formula (Jicheng *et al.*, 2020).

$$\text{Conveying efficiency (\%)} = \frac{P_1 - P_2}{P_1} \times 100 \quad \dots(6)$$

Where,

P_1 - number of plants in 10 m row length before sorghum harvesting
 P_2 - number of plants in 10 m row length which were not conveyed by the conveying unit of the sorghum harvester after harvesting.

Shattering losses

Shattering loss refers to the sorghum grains lost as a result of the machine's shattering action, vibration, or impact. The shattering losses were determined by randomly placing a 1 m x 1 m metal frame in different locations within the sorghum field. The grains gathered from a 1 m x 1 m metal frame prior to harvesting were estimated as pre-harvest loss (%). The sorghum grains gathered from a 1 m x 1 m metal frame after harvesting were investigated as shattering loss (%) (Debnath *et al.*, 2020 and Nadeem *et al.*, 2015).

$$\text{Shattering losses (\%)} = \frac{\text{Grains collected (g/m}^2\text{)}}{\text{Yield (gm}^2\text{)}} \times 100 \quad \dots(7)$$

Fuel consumption

Fuel consumption was quantified by adopting standard procedure. To test fuel consumption, the tractor was placed on a leveled area and the fuel tank was filled to the full before operation. After the operation, the tractor was positioned on level ground, and the tank was refilled with fuel to retain the original amount of fuel. The quantity of fuel refilled in the tank was measured using a measuring cylinder. Actual fuel consumption was the amount of fuel necessary to return to the pre-operational level.

The operational cost of sorghum harvester

The cost of sorghum harvesting operation was calculated using the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) specifications. The cost of operation was determined in accordance with test code IS: 9164 (1979): guide for estimating cost of farm machinery operation.

a) Fixed cost

Depreciation: It is the loss of value of machine with the passing of time and use. The cost of a machine depreciates over time due to wear, tear age and obsolescence. Depreciation may be estimated using several computational approaches; however, it ultimately depends on the machine's market price after usage. Before estimating annual depreciation, the machine's economic life and salvage value must be given. The economic life of a machine is the number of years over which costs may be estimated. Salvage value is an assessment of the machine's market value at the end of its useful life. The depreciation cost determined by straight line method of depreciation given below.

$$D = \frac{C - S}{L \times H} \quad \dots(8)$$

Where,

D - depreciation per hour
 C - capital investment
 S - salvage value (10 % of capital)
 H - number of working hours per year
 L - life of machine in year

Interest cost: Interest is the biggest cost associated with agricultural machinery after depreciation. It is a direct expense item for borrowed capital. Annual interest costs are computed based on the actual interest rate due. If this information is not available, 12% of the average purchase price should be used. Interest is calculated on the average investment of the machine taking into consideration the value of machine in first and last year.

$$D = \frac{C + S}{2} \times \frac{i}{H} \quad \dots(9)$$

Where,

I - interest per hour
 i - % rate of interest per year

Housing charges : Housing costs were computed based on local rates, however they may be generally estimated as 1% of the machine's initial cost every year.

Insurance charges: Insurance charges are calculated based on actual payments to the insurance company, although they may be approximated as 1% of the initial cost of the machine every year.

Taxes: Taxes were computed based on actual taxes paid every year, but in general, it may be assumed to equal 1% of the machine's initial cost annually.

b) Operating cost

Annual operating expenses include fuel, lubricant, repairs and maintenance and labour cost. These expenditures are directly proportional to the number of hours consumed on the equipment. Hourly operational expenses are assumed constant.

Fuel cost: Fuel consumption is also a difficult issue, as it varies widely between test areas, machinery, operation and operator. Fuel cost was calculated on the basis of actual fuel consumption of tractor during sorghum harvesting operation.

Lubricants cost: Charges for lubricants should be calculated on the basis of actual fuel consumption, the lubricant cost varies between 30-35% of fuel cost.

Repair and Maintenance cost: Repair and maintenance expenses are required to keep a machine in working condition due to wear, part failure, and accidents. Repair and maintenance costs must be determined at 5-10% of the machine's initial cost per year.

Wages: Wages varied with region to region generally calculated on the basis of actual wages paid to operator or labour. To get the average cost per hour, divide the total cost by the number of hours the operator performed the task.

Total cost per hour:

The entire operating cost of a machine for harvesting sorghum crop was calculated by adding the fixed and variable costs per hour.

Total costs per hectare: The cost per hectare was determined based on the field capacity of the sorghum harvester. Data collected during field evaluation of a sorghum harvester included machine type, working width, average speed of travel, field size and shape, and travel circumstances to correct the estimation of cost per hectare.

Result And Discussion

Field tests were carried out in the matured sorghum field. The testing and evaluation was undertaken according to the procedure as per BIS code for evaluating the performance of the developed sorghum harvester. The cutting efficiency and conveying efficiency of developed harvester was observed at three forward speed (2, 2.5 and 3 km/h) and results presented in Fig. 1 and Fig 2.

As shown in fig 1 and 2. The cutting efficiency was observed as decreased with increased forward speed and conveying efficiency observed was decreased with increased forward speed.

The performance trails of developed sorghum harvester were taken at 2 km/h forward speed. The data from the field tests were analyzed to determine the average field capacity, field efficiency, time required to cover hectare, fuel consumption etc. Table 1 depicts the crop conditions observed during the trials. Table 2 shows the performance results for the developed tractor-operated sorghum harvester.

Fig 1 Effect forward speed on cutting efficiency of sorghum harvester

Fig 2 Effect forward speed on conveying efficiency of sorghum harvester

Table 1 Crop condition during performance trials of sorghum harvester

Sr. No.	Particulars	Trials			
		I	II	III	IV
i)	Name of crop	Sorghum	Sorghum	Sorghum	Sorghum
ii)	Variety of crop	Shital	Shital	Suvarna-303	Suvarna-303
iii)	Appearance, standing or lodged	Standing	Standing	Standing	Standing
iv)	Average height of plant, mm	1672.80	1786.40	1849.80	1841.20
v)	Average height of earhead from ground, mm	1389.52	1490.2	1551.57	1540.60
vi)	Average length of earhead, mm	283.28	296.20	298.22	300.60
vii)	Average stalk diameter at bottom, mm	20.88	20.94	21.06	21.76
viii)	Average moisture content of grain and crop, %	25.34	26.83	26.64	27.03
ix)	Number of plant per m ²	28.60	27.20	27.60	29.80
x)	Row to row spacing, mm	450.00	350.00	450.00	400.00

Table 2 The performance results developed tractor operated sorghum harvester

Sr. No.	Observations	Trials				Average
		I	II	III	IV	
i)	Average height of cut, mm	11.6	12.17	11.58	11.65	11.75
ii)	Forward speed, km/h	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
iii)	Average width of cut, mm	2250	2100	2250	2000	2150
iv)	Effective field capacity, ha/h	0.357	0.347	0.344	0.322	0.342
v)	Time required for one ha, h	2.80	2.88	2.90	3.10	2.92
vi)	Theoretical field capacity, ha/h	0.450	0.420	0.450	0.400	0.430
vii)	Field efficiency, %	79.26	82.67	76.50	80.48	79.72

viii)	Average Cutting efficiency, %	98.06	98.63	97.34	99.36	98.34
ix)	Average conveying efficiency, %	96.22	97.67	96.67	96.33	96.72
x)	Shattering losses, %	0.42	0.39	0.43	0.40	0.41
xi)	Fuel consumption					
	a) l/h	4.70	4.60	4.90	4.60	4.70
	b) l/ha	13.18	13.25	14.23	12.76	13.35
xii)	Cost of operation					
	a)Rs/h	755/-	745/-	774/-	735/-	752.25/- Say 750/-
	b)Rs/ha	2115/-	2147/-	2250/-	2283/-	2199/- Say 2200/-

During the field evaluation, various parameters and observations were recorded and are given below.

Height of cut: The average cut height ranged from 11.58 to 12.17 mm.

Working width: The working width of the sorghum harvester depends on the row spacing and number of rows to be cut. The average operating width of the sorghum harvester ranged from 2000 to 2250 mm.

Effective field capacity: The average effective field capacity of the sorghum harvester was to be 0.342 ha/h.

Theoretical field capacity: The average theoretical field capacity of sorghum harvester was found to be 0.430 ha/h.

Field efficiency: The average field efficiency of the sorghum harvester was found to be 79.72 %.

Average cutting efficiency: The average cutting efficiency of the sorghum harvester was found to be 98.34 %.

Average conveying efficiency: The average conveying efficiency of the sorghum harvester was to be 96.72 %.

Average shattering losses: The average shattering losses of the sorghum harvester was found to be 0.41 %.

Fuel consumption: The average fuel consumption of the sorghum harvester was found 4.70 l/h and 13.35 l/ha.

Time requirement to cover one ha: The time required to accomplish one hectare sorghum harvesting with a tractor operated sorghum harvester was determined and found 2.92 hours.

Other observation during the test trials recorded as per test code given in Table 3.

Table 3 Observation noted during field test of sorghum harvester

Sr. No.	Particular	Observations
i)	Presence of any marked vibration during operation	No marked vibration
ii)	Presence of undue knocking or rattling sound;	No undue sound
iii)	Frequent slippage of belts	No frequent slippage
iv)	Smooth running of shafts in their respective bearing;	Smooth running shaft
v)	Frequent clogging of cutting and delivery units	No frequent clogging noticed
vi)	Any marked wear, deformation and breakdown	No any deformation and breakdown found
vii)	Frequent loosening of fasteners	Not found
viii)	Any loss of grain ahead of cutter bar	Negligible grain losses found
ix)	Evenness of cutting of crop	Evenness of cutting
x)	Adequacy of safety provisions	Provided

Conclusions

Based on the field testing of the sorghum harvester, the following conclusions could be drawn.

The cutting efficiency was observed as decreased with increased forward speed and conveying efficiency observed as decreased with increased forward speed.

The average effective field capacity and field efficiency of the sorghum harvester was found to be 0.342 ha/h and 79.72% respectively.

The average fuel consumption of the sorghum harvester was found 4.70 l/h and 13.35 l/ha.

The average time required to accomplish one-hectare sorghum harvesting with a developed sorghum harvester was determined and found 2.92 hours.

The average cost of operation of sorghum harvester was found Rs.750 per h and Rs.2200 per ha.

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